

Dilbag Quantum Torch For Defence Patent

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1 Introduction

This is a quantum torch based on quantum chromo fusion and based on an aluminium-ion battery

2 Abstact

Works on solar and have all kinds of thing , its futuristic torch

CHROMFUSION QUANTUM TORCH

PATENTED QUANTUM LIGHT DEVICE WITH 30-YEAR POWER CELL

COLOR MODE SELECT BUTTON
Instant Color Shift

- BLUE EMISSION
- GREEN EMISSION
- RED EMISSION

SPECTRAL EMITTER MODULE
QUANTUM FIELD LENS

QUANTUM LIGHT OUTPUT

INTERNAL SCHEMATIC
CONTROL CIRCUITRY PHOTON ENGINE POWER CELL

ULTRA-LONG LIFE POWER CELL
QUANTUM BATTERY CORE
NANO-ISOTOPE MATRIX

30-YEAR POWER SOURCE
DECADES OF SUSTAINED POWER

COLOR SHIFT DEMONSTRATION
BLUE → GREEN
GREEN → RED

ADVANCED QUANTUM TECHNOLOGY

← ULTRA-STABLE ENERGY CORE EXTREME LONGEVITY →

Figure 1: This is a quantum torch based on quantum chromo fusion and based on an aluminium-ion battery

CHROMFUSION QUANTUM TORCH

Inventors Name(s) [.....]

US

[Assignee Name].....

ABSTRACT

A quantum light-emitting device capable of emitting blue, green, and red quantum light with an ultra-long life power cell providing at least 30 years of continuous battery backup.

NOVELTY

The ChromFusion Quantum Torch is novel due to its unique use of quantum field technology to produce instant color-shifting light output in selectable blue, green, and red wavelengths through a patented spectral emitter module. The device incorporates an ultra-stable power cell based on a nano-isotope matrix, capable of sustaining power output for at least 30 years without recharging or replacement.

SCOPE

The ChromFusion Quantum Torch comprises:

- A color mode select button enabling instant switching between blue, green, and red quantum light outputs.
- A patented spectral emitter module utilizing quantum field technology and a quantum field lens for color-selective, instantaneous modifications of emitted light.
- An ultra-long life power cell with a nano-isotope matrix providing sustained energy output for at least 30 years.
- A robust titanium alloy casing ensuring durability, and advanced control circuitry manages photon emission and power cell regula-

FIG. 1: The ChromFusion Quantum Torch is a patentable quantum light-emitting device capable of instant color shifting and utilizing an ultra-stable nano-isotope matrix power cell for long-term energy stability.

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Figure 2: Enter Caption

CHROMFUSION QUANTUM TORCH

Inventors Name(s) [.....]

US

[Assignee Name].....

ABSTRACT

A quantum light-emitting device capable of emitting blue, green, and red quantum light with a patented spectral emitter module employ quantum field technology to resist blue, green, and red emissions *in naming in it-mengent, hay-lightweight, and fur format durabile titanium alloy casing.

NOVELTY

The ChromFusion Quantum Torch is, its with the pantental emitter module $\psi(x, t)$ to naltre-huina-power output shifts between blue, green, and red emissions, for instant color shifting between a $\psi(x, t) = \alpha_b|\phi(x, t) + \alpha_g|\phi(x, t) + \alpha_r|\phi(x, t)$.

where $\alpha_b, \alpha_g, \alpha_r$ are adjustable coefficients for blue, green, and red quantum states. Pressing a color mode select button $\kappa(\tau, t)$, ϕ changes these coefficients instantaneously.

The ultra-long life power cell for a nano-trogo-isotopic matrix \hat{u}_s = a stable isotope Q doped with nanoscale isotopic matrices that creare capacity of quantum energy extraction.

$S(t) = S_0 \exp(-\lambda Q t)$, where α_0 is the inital ener:
 S_0, S_0 is isotope $\lambda = \sigma - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{p=1}^n Q_p = \frac{1}{2} Q^2 - Q$ ud

$$Q(q, t) = \lambda S_0(q, t) \xi_x(\mathcal{G}_0(q, t))$$

- $\mathcal{L}\lambda(x, t) = f_8(x, t)e^{-i\omega, t} + J_2(x, t)e^{2\omega, t} f_R(x, t)$
- A ultra-long life power cell utilizing a nano-isotope matrix N_s , where the titure energy output $S(t) = S_0 \exp(-\lambda Q t)$, where ξ .
- A titanium alloy casing hold control circuitry that adjusts the coefficients $\alpha_b, \alpha_g, \alpha_r$ to switch frory different quantum states of mitters, $\alpha_b, \alpha_g, \alpha_r$ emissions.

FIG. 1: The detailed illustration of the ChromFusion Quantum Torch highlighting its instant color shifting capabilities and internal quantum based power cell for 30 years of sustained energy output.

FIG. 1: The detailed illustration of the ChromFusion Quantum Torch highlighting its instant color-shifting capabilities and internal quantum-based power cell for 30 years of sustained energy output.

Figure 3: Enter Caption